

Influence of storage containers on the physicochemical and microbiological (biofilm formation) indices of drinking water sources

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ABSTRACT

Effect of surfaces of earthenware pots, glass, plastic and stainless steel containers on the physicochemical and bacteriological (biofilm formation) quality of borehole and atmospheric water stored for twelve days were determined using standard analytical and bacteriological techniques. Susceptibility of the bacterial isolates to different antibiotics was also determined using standard Kirby-Bauer agar disc diffusion procedures. The physicochemical parameters determined for borehole water sample were within WHO permissible standard while rain water sample recorded slightly higher values for NO_3^- , and NO_2^- (10.2 mgL^{-1} and 0.045 mgL^{-1} respectively) than WHO standards of 10 mgL^{-1} and 0.02 mgL^{-1} respectively. Biofilm bacterial communities from stored borehole water consisted of nine genera including *Pseudomonas*, *Micrococcus*, *Klebsiella*, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Escherichia*, *Proteus*, *Serratia*, and *Enterobacter*. The recovery rate of the various bacterial genera were 40% in earthenware pot, 80% in plastic, 70% in stainless steel and 60% of the genera were isolated from glass container for stored borehole water. Fewer bacterial genera were isolated from stored atmospheric water and these included *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *Yersinia*. The isolates were recovered at the rates of 40%, 80%, 60% and 40% in earthenware pot, plastic, stainless steel and glass containers respectively. While *Escherichia coli*, *Yersinia* sp and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* exhibited remarkable sensitivity to Septrin (30 μg), Ampicillin (30 μg), Augmentin (30 μg) and Nalidixic acid (10 μg) as evinced by clear zones of inhibition, *Enterobacter* sp, *Klebsiella* sp and *Proteus* sp were moderately sensitive to some of the tested antibiotics. Amongst the gram positive bacteria, *Micrococcus* sp was most sensitive to the various antibiotics. Although *Staphylococcus aureus* showed resistance to most of the tested antibiotics, it was sensitive to Erythromycin (30 μg) and Chloramphenicol (30 μg). It could be deduced from the above results that the physicochemical and bacteriological quality of stored water are affected by both the source of the water and type of storage vessel. Although the effect of the vessels are not definitive, the levels of pH, Mg^{2+} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- and hardness are enhanced in water stored in earthenware pots. The isolation of antibiotic resistant bacteria from stored water is of public health concern, thus, drinking water should not be held in containers for more than a day or two.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The diversity and prevalence of bacteria is astonishing. Bacteria are adept at adapting to their extracellular conditions, which has made it possible for them to establish themselves in nearly all habitats in the biosphere [20]. Thus, bacteria are ubiquitous, inhabiting diverse habitat and are found living freely in soil and

aquatic systems while most are found attached to surfaces with majority forming biofilms. Biofilm formation is an important phenomenon in nature and are developed as one of the survival strategies since bacteria are exposed to sanitizers and antimicrobials regularly in aquatic system [6].

A biofilm is a well-organized, cooperating com-

munity of microorganisms [14]. The densely packed microbial cells grow on living or inert surfaces and surround themselves with secreted polymers [15]. Biofilms exist on many types of surfaces such as plastic, metal, glass, soil particles, wood, medical implants, tissues and food products. The attachment is facilitated by cell structures such as fimbriae, pili, flagella and extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) that acts to form a bridge between bacteria and the conditioning film [9]. Thus biofilm is composed, primarily of micro-colonies of different species of EPS and microbial cells. The EPS may vary in chemical and physical properties, but primarily consists of polysaccharides. The presence of Uronic acid (D-glucouronic, D-galactouronic and Mannuronic) or ketal linked pyruvate confers on it anionic properties. This property helps in association of divalent cations such as calcium and magnesium which forms a cross-link with the polymer strands to provide greater binding force in a developed biofilm [8]. The amount of EPS produced by different organisms vary, and increases with the age of biofilm.

Microbial cells growing in a biofilm are physiologically distinct from planktonic cells of the same organism, which by contrast, are single-cells that may float or swim in a liquid medium. Microbes form biofilms in response to many factors, which may include cellular recognition of specific attachment sites on a surface, nutritional cues or exposure of cells to sub-inhibitory concentrations of antimicrobials [10, 12]. When a cell switches to the biofilm mode of growth, it undergoes a phenotypic shift in behaviour in which large suites of genes are differently regulated [1].

Microscopic analysis has indicated that biofilm formation occurs in a sequential process of transport of microbes to a surface, initial attachment, formation of microcolonies and biofilm maturation [13]. Many physical, chemical and biological interactions facilitate the attachment of bacteria to surfaces. The interactions between the bacterial cell wall and surfaces are primarily influenced by interfacial electrostatic (repulsion and attraction) and Van der Waals forces. However, other non-specific interactions and interfacial forces influencing cell attachment include hydration forces, hydrophobic interactions and steric forces [22]. Many studies have concluded that individual physical properties of surfaces, such as mentioned previously, may have dramatic impact on bacterial attachment [21].

Most bacterial genera have a net negative charge as determined by Zeta-potential measurement [21], thus bacteria attach rapidly and tightly to positively charged surfaces, while electrostatic repulsion destabilizes cell contact with negatively charged surfaces. Preferential alignment of hydrophobic functional groups on surfaces and hydrophobic moieties on the bacterial cell wall and extracellular organelles, stabilizes interfacial interactions [21]. The

authors studied bacterial attachment in nutrient-free media, to avoid nutrient remodeling the surface and concluded that physical interactions between cell surfaces and substrate were responsible for attachment.

The manipulation of individual environmental factors to prevent biofilm formation has been met with limited success. Control over surface chemistry has been used to reduce cell attachment, including the development of dynamic surfaces that degrade or reorganizes in response to temperature and other environmental conditions and shed adsorbed bacteria into the bulk fluid [18]. Also, surface restructuring has been explored by engineering high-aspect ratio topographical features that decrease surface wettability and render it superhydrophobic.

Surface-associated communities protect bacteria from predators and the immune system, support the division of labour and provide a physical and structural barrier against mechanical and physical stimulations [20]. These communities may be persistent and difficult to remove once formed. The formation of these communities and their inherent resistance to antimicrobial agents are the cause of many persistent and chronic infections. Thus, efforts to understand their mechanism of growth and homeostasis have broad application in biomedicine, dentistry, ecology, agriculture, industrial processing [20] and in the home environment.

Water is the most abundant and essential requirement of man. It is obtained from harvesting of atmospheric water such as rain, hail, snow and surface water such as streams, ponds, rivers or ground water such as springs, wells and boreholes. Ground water is a vital source of water in places experiencing prolonged dry season and accounts for about 95% of global fresh water supplies [17]. Rain water on the other hand becomes available only during the wet season and this seasonal distribution contributes to scarcity of the commodity.

Due to scarcity, consumers are compelled to store water in various containers sometime for prolonged periods. World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that up to 80% of ill health in developing countries is water and sanitation related. Although water contamination could be from chemicals, the greatest risk to human health is from faecal contamination resulting in water borne diseases [5]. On the other hand, storage containers including tanks and reservoirs serve as possible sources of contamination due to development of biofilm.

In the present study, we seek to investigate the effect of surfaces of some house-hold water storage containers on the potability of water using biofilm community development and changes in the physiochemical properties of

such stored water as indices and also determine the sensitivity of the microbial community to commercial antibiotics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection of water samples

2.1.1 Rain water

Rain water was harvested directly from the atmosphere into a sterile aluminium basin placed on a stool (1.5m high from the ground). The water was dispensed into five sets each of pre-sterilized plastics, earthen ware pots, glass, stainless steel containers (4 litres capacity) and covered normally.

2.1.2 Borehole water

Borehole water was collected into another sets of containers as in above.

2.2 Processing of water samples

The water samples were placed on a work bench at a corner in the Microbiology Laboratory, University of Uyo, where they remained undisturbed for 14 days at ambient temperature.

The samples were subjected to microbiological analyses on day 1, 3, 6, 9 and 12; and physiochemical analyses at the beginning and at the end of storage period.

2.2.1 Microbiological analysis

Microbiological analysis of the walls of the containing vessels was carried out every three days beginning from day 1 to determine the bacterial diversity associated with the surfaces. Water was carefully removed from the storage vessels using a siphon. The walls of the vessels were then scrubbed with a sterile swab stick and thereafter used to inoculate tubes containing 10mls of nutrient broth. The tubes were agitated thoroughly to dislodge the microorganisms from the swab and incubated at room temperature for 6 hours before a 2-fold dilution was done. From the dilutions, pour plate procedure was carried out using nutrient agar, McConkey agar, Eosin Methylene blue, Salmonella shigella agar and Thiosulphate citrate bile salt agar. The plates were incubated at 30°C for between 24 and 48 hours.

2.2.2 Isolation, characterization and identification of members of biofilm communities

Representative colonies on the culture plates were picked and repeatedly subcultured on nutrient agar. Pure isolates were examined on the basis of their cultural, macroscopic and microscopic characteristic before being subjected to various biochemical tests according to the procedure of [5]. The properties derived

from the tests for the various isolates were collated, and identification carried out by comparing the characteristic of known taxa using the schemes of [7] and [11].

Physiochemical Analysis

The following physical and chemical parameters in the water samples were analysed before and at the end of the storage period using standard analytical techniques. These include colour, turbidity, pH, electrical conductivity, nutritive cations and anions (Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-}), hardness, dissolved oxygen and metal ions (Pb^{2+} , Fe^{3+}) [2, 19,4] were determined.

2.2.3 Antibiotic sensitivity testing

Susceptibility of the various bacterial isolates from the biofilm communities to different antibiotics were determined using Bauer disc-diffusion technique [3]. Sterile petri dishes of Mueller-Hinton agar were prepared. About 0.1ml of an 18hr old culture of the test organisms was seeded onto the Mueller-Hinton agar plates and allowed to stand for 45 minutes before commercial discs [containing ciprofloxacin (Cip 10µg), Norfloxacin (Nor 10 µg), Gentamycin (Gen. 10µg) Linocin (Lin 20µg), Streptomycin (Str 30µg), Rifampicin (Rif 20µg), Erythromycin (Ery 30µg), Chloramphenicol (Chl 30µg), Ampiclox (Amp 20µg) and Floxapen (Flo 20µg) (Oxoid, UK)] were aseptically placed on the surface of the already seeded plates and incubated at 37°C for between 18 and 24 hrs. The zones of inhibition were measured in millimeter at the end of the incubation. Interpretation of the measurement as resistant, moderately sensitive and sensitive was done based on the manufacturer's (ABTEK MANUAL) standard zone size interpretative manual. The moderately sensitive readings were considered as sensitive for the assessment of the data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physiochemical properties of borehole and rain water samples before and after storage in selected containers are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The results revealed that while all parameters determined for the borehole water sample were within WHO permissible standards except for NO_3^- , rain water sample recorded slightly higher values for nitrite in addition to nitrate (0.045mg/L and 10.2mg/L respectively) than WHO standard of 0.02mg/L (NO_2^-) and 10.0mg/L (NO_3^-).

Tables 3 and 4 contain results of the distribution of bacterial communities in biofilms formed on surfaces of the different vessels used in storing borehole and rain water samples. The biofilm bacterial communities in the borehole water sample consisted of nine bacterial genera, including *Pseudomonas*, *Micrococcus*, *Klebsiella*, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Proteus*, *Serratia*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia*. Forty

percent of these bacterial genera were recovered from earthenware pot whereas 80%, 70% and 60% of the isolated genera were encountered in plastic, stainless steel and glass containers respectively. On the other hand, five bacterial genera including *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *Yersinia* were isolated from rain water samples with a genera recovery rate of 40%, 30%, 60% and 40% in earthenware pot, plastic, stainless

steel and glass containers. While *Pseudomonas* sp, *Staphylococcus* sp, *Bacillus* sp and *Micrococcus* sp occurred in that order of decreasing magnitude in biofilms formed in borehole water stored in the various vessels, however, the organisms were restricted to *Pseudomonas* sp, *Bacillus* sp and *Staphylococcus* sp in vessels containing stored rain water.

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of borehole water before and after storage in different containing vessels.

Parameters	Before Storage	After Storage in			
		Plastic Container	Earthenware Container	Glass Container	WHO Standard
Turbidity (NTU)	0.30	0.40	3.40	0.30	5.0
Colour (TCU)	1.00	1.40	2.10	1.20	1.0-1.5
pH	6.82	7.00	8.20*	7.00	6.5 – 8.5
Electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)	0.746	200	500	200	1000
Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.23	0.05	1.97*	0.29	0.02
Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.80	1.05	3.20	0.40	7.5
Na ⁺ (mg/L)	0.24	0.28	1.62	0.04	2.00
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.004	2.50
NO ₂ ⁻ (mg/L)	0.001	0.56	0.88	0.49	0.02
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	1.20*	0.014	1.98*	0.02	1.0
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	0.001	0.001	0.002	ND	0.002
Hardness (CaCO ₃ mg/L)	0.070	0.085	46.00*	0.78	15.0
Dissolved Oxygen (Mg/L)	6.20	6.70	7.20	6.00	7.2
Pb ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.01	0.5
Fe ³⁺ (mg/L)	0.06	0.06	0.73	0.014	0.3

ND = Not Determined

* = Values above WHO standard

Table 2. Physicochemical properties of rain water before and after storage in different containing vessels.

Parameters	Before Storage	After Storage in			
		Plastic Container	Earthenware Container	Glass Container	WHO Standard
Turbidity (NTU)	0.5	0.7	4.0	0.5	5.0
Colour (TCU)	1.0	1.95	5.18	1.87	1.0-1.5
pH	5.8*	6.95	8.5*	6.90	6.5 – 8.5
Electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)	1.045	400	700	300	1000
Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.42*	0.09	2.90*	0.05	0.02
Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.12	0.15	9.2	0.3	7.50
Na ⁺ (mg/L)	0.28	0.33	1.61	0.21	2.00
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.001	0.006	0.005	0.06	2.50
NO ₂ ⁻ (mg/L)	0.045*	1.20*	4.05*	1.00*	0.02
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	10.2	10.05	11.098	10.02	10
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	0.004	0.004	0.006	ND	0.002
Hardness (CaCO ₃ mg/L)	0.094	0.097	1158	0.067	15.0
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	7.5	7.9	8.3	7.6	7.2
Pb ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.001	0.003	0.01	0.02	0.5
Fe ³⁺ (mg/L)	0.02	0.03	1.12	0.02	0.3

ND = Not Determined

* = Values above WHO standard

Table 3. Bacterial dynamics in biofilm from different storage vessels containing borehole water.

Containing Vessel	Day 1	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Day 12
Earthenware Pot	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp
Plastic	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Micrococcus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Micrococcus</i> sp <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp, <i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp <i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Proteus</i> sp. <i>Klebsiella</i> sp <i>Enterobacter</i> sp <i>Serratia</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Micrococcus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp, <i>Proteus</i> sp, <i>Enterobacter</i> sp <i>Serratia</i> sp
Stainless Steel	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Micrococcus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp <i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp <i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp, <i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Proteus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp
Glass	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Micrococcus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Klebsiella</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp, <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> <i>Micrococcus</i> sp, <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Micrococcus</i> sp

Table 4. Bacterial Dynamics in Biofilm from different Storage Vessels Containing Rain water

Containing Vessel	Day 1	Day 3	Day 6	Day 9	Day 12
Earthenware Pot	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp
Plastic	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> <i>Bacillus</i> _sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i> sp.	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp, <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i> sp <i>Yersinia</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Streptococcus</i> sp <i>Yersinia</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>Streptococcus</i> sp <i>Yersinia</i> sp
Stainless Steel	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> _sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp, <i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp <i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp, <i>S. epidermidis</i>
Glass	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>

Table 5. Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of Gram Positive Bacterial members of a Biofilm Community.

Antibiotic (µg)	Zone of Inhibition (mm diameter)				
	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Streptococcus</i> sp	<i>Bacillus</i> sp	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
Ciprofloxacin (10)	15	13	11	14	16
Norfloxacin (10)	17	12	14	19*	14
Gentamycin (10)	17	10	12	18*	16
Lincocin (20)	19*	15	13	20*	13
Streptomycin (30)	18*	14	12	19*	19*
Rifampicin (20)	20*	17	13	15	14
Erythromycin (30)	19*	18*	16	13	15
Chloramphenical (30)	18*	18*	16	15	16
Ampiclox (20)	20*	12	14	16	17
Floxapen (20)	16	12	13	13	18*

ABTEK Manual Interpretation

0 – 13mm = Resistant

14 – 17mm = Moderately sensitive

*18mm and above = Sensitive

Table 6. Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of Gram negative bacterial members of a biofilm community.

Antibiotic (µg)	Zone of Inhibition (mm diameter)						
	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i> sp	<i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>Serratia</i> sp	<i>Yersinia</i> sp	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Ciprofloxacin (10)	14	13	14	15	12	16	14
Streptomycin (30)	16	18*	16	17	15	18*	19*
Peflacin (10)	10	16	13	14	16	17	17
Seprin (30)	16	23*	14	20*	21*	20*	22*
Ampicillin (30)	14	20*	8	21*	19*	21*	20*
Tarivid (10)	10	12	13	15	16	18*	14
Ceporex (10)	10	10	14	17	18*	20*	16
Gentamycin (10)	13	18*	19*	16.	18*	18	17
Augmentin (30)	17	19*	14	20*	21*	19	20*
Nalidixic acid (10)	19*	18*	17	18	20*	20*	18*

ABTEK Manual Interpretation

0 – 13mm = Resistant

14 – 17mm = Moderately sensitive

*18mm and above = Sensitive

All members of the bacterial communities isolated in the biofilms were subjected to standard antibiotic sensitivity testing. The results presented in Table 5, indicates the antibiotic sensitivity profile of Gram positive bacteria, while Table 6 reveals the sensitivity pattern of Gram negative bacterial isolates.

Most of the Gram negative bacteria isolated exhibited marked sensitivity to Seprin (30µg), Ampicillin (30µg), Augmentin (30µg) and Nalidixic acid (10µg). While *E. coli*, *Yersinia* sp and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* apparently were susceptible to most of the antibiotic assayed, *Enterobacter* sp, *Klebsiella* sp and *Proteus* sp were relatively resistant. Amongst the Gram positive, *Micrococcus* sp was the most sensitive bacteria to the various antibiotics. Although *Staphylococcus aureus* showed resistance or moderate sensitivity to most of the antibiotics, they were however, sensitive to both chloramphenicol (30µg) and Erythromycin (30µg). Streptococcal isolates were particularly very resistant to most of the antibiotics except where they exhibited moderate sensitivity to Erythromycin and Chloramphenicol.

It is evidenced from the results of this research that the effect of the containing vessel on the physicochemical properties of stored borehole water was more pronounced in earthenware pots as it recorded higher levels for pH (8.20), Mg^{2+} (1.97mg/L) and NO_3^- (1.98mg/L). Although, the initial NO_3^- concentration of (1.20mg/L) in the borehole water sample before storage was higher than WHO permissible standard (1.0mg/L). The enhanced level in the

4. CONCLUSION

From the results obtained in this study, it is evident that the physicochemical and bacteriological qualities of stored drinking water

earthenware pot (1.98mg/L) is suggestive of the dissolution and possible ionization of chemicals from the surfaces of the vessel into the bulk water. These observations become apparent when one compares the values of parameter such as pH, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , NO_3^- and hardness for earthenware pot containers with that of other containers. It is also obvious from the results of this research that rain water harvested in the study area is of acidic pH and the effect of this on biota cannot be overemphasized. This indicates that the atmosphere over the area contains gaseous pollutants possibly emitted as a result of anthropogenic activities related to petroleum exploration, exploitation and more importantly gas flaring.

The high levels of nitrate and other parameter found in both water samples stored in earthenware pots and the low pH rain water harvested gives some concern because of the health implications involved. Excessive nitrate as noted by [16] causes blue-baby syndrome, a condition in which a baby appears blue due to oxygen starvation as a result of reduction of nitrate to nitrite in the infant's intestine.

The hydroxyl ion content of rain and borehole water samples stored in earthenware pots were above neutral, suggesting the presence of basic compounds. The reddish brown colour of the water sample in the pots may be due to interaction between Fe^{3+} and OH^- present in the water resulting in the formation of $[Fe(H_2O)_5]^{3+}$ complex. According to [17], the iron could result from the clay materials used in making the pots. are affected by source of water, the surface of the containing vessels and duration of storage. The rate of biofilm formation in the containers which were of the order of magnitude; earthen ware pot<glass container<stainless steel container<plastic container suggest the earthen

ware pot as a better vessel, however, the observed enhanced levels of Mg^{2+} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- and hardness in its content present a public health issue. Nevertheless, storage of drinking water in vessels for more than a day or two should be discouraged.

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